

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE)_Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection if prevalence increases; Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution; Early detection of an increase in incidence.
3	Target species and group	Hard ticks – Genus <i>Ixodes</i> .
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	Areas with high-risk of disease prevalence; areas where LB has been previously diagnosed; areas with recent tick vector expansion; preferred habitats of hard ticks: shady and humid woodlands, trails (1), clearings with grass, open fields and bushes, urban and rural areas. (2)
6	Age group	Adults and nymphs.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Flagging a cloth in suitable vector habitat to collect questing ticks. (1)
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited; ticks, are most active from March to November. (2)
9	Sampling matrix	Adult and nymphal tick body.
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of the pathogen, identification of TBEV.
11	Sampling unit	Pooled flagged ticks by location/life stage – max pool of 5 adults or 10 nymphs at least 1000 individuals per sampling location. – pooling ticks from animals – max pool of 5 half ticks (other half for virus isolation & prevalence) [VectorNet, 2022]
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	All collected adults and nymphs.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	PCR on pooled tick samples.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component is not expected to have a high sensitivity. [VectorNet, 2022]
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever (CCHF), Lyme Borreliosis (LB), Anaplasma phagocytophilum, Rickettsia spp., Neoehrlichia mikurensis and zoonotic Babesia spp. (3)
18	References	<p>1) Salomon J, Hamer SA, Swei A. A Beginner's Guide to Collecting Questing Hard Ticks (Acari: Ixodidae): A Standardized Tick Dragging Protocol. J Insect Sci. 2020 Nov 1;20(6):11. doi: 10.1093/jisesa/ieaa073. PMID: 33135760; PMCID: PMC7604844.</p> <p>2) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–2018</p> <p>3) Springer A, Glass A, Topp AK, Strube C. Zoonotic Tick-Borne Pathogens in Temperate and Cold Regions of Europe-A Review on the Prevalence in Domestic Animals. Front Vet Sci. 2020 Dec 10;7:604910. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2020.604910. PMID: 33363242; PMCID: PMC7758354.</p>